

INNOVATIVE CLOTHING MODELING METHODS

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ABSTRACT

The article on clothing design provides that many clothing models do not have significant differences in the design of the main parts and differ from each other precisely by model features. Therefore, a large number of models can be represented by a limited number of basic clothing designs, modeling basic patterns.

Introduction.

Clothing modeling is the transformation of the basic design of a product in order to change its model characteristics.

There are several types of transformation of the basic structure:

- 1) without changing the shape of the product
- 2) changing the silhouette, without changing the volumetric shape in the area of the support areas
- 3) a complete change in the volumetric shape
- 4) changing the cut of the sleeve
- 5) obtaining new clothing models of complex shapes and hybrid designs

Let's take a closer look at structural transformations and basic modeling techniques.

The relevance of research. Modeling the basic structure without changing the shape of the structure itself includes: transferring darts in different directions, transferring division lines, combining parts

(excluding seams) or further dividing them into smaller parts, designing folds, developing model features of a collar, lapel, side, pockets, small parts, loops, buttons.

Research results.

A tuck is a constructive technique with the help of which the volumetric shape of the product is achieved and a uniform fitting with a flat material of a complex body configuration. The bust dart is always directed to the center of the chest and can be transferred to the armhole, side cut, mid-front line, waist, neckline.

Modeling method: development of decorative elements of the main units of the product

Modeling techniques

The modeling of the basic structure with a change in the silhouette, but without changing the shape of the volume in the area of the support areas includes: moving the waist line, increasing or decreasing the fit along the waist line, expanding or narrowing the product downward, etc. Transformation

of the basic pattern is achieved by methods

of parallel expansion or conical expansion ...

Modeling method: parallel expansion

Parallel expansion is used to design soft assemblies or folds on part parts. To do this, the location of the folds is applied to the part, then the part is cut into parts in accordance with the lines drawn and moved apart by the required amount. Depending on the garment model, the expansion of the

details may be uniform or uneven. An expanded part is obtained by gradually moving the part and tracing the outer contours of the stripes. The final contours of the converted sections of the part are drawn up with curved curves: assemblies - with a smooth curve; folds, tucks - broken straight lines.

Modeling method: conical expansion

The conical expansion of garment parts, depending on the designed model, can begin at any level: the line of the shoulders, chest, waist, hips, knees and below. Determination of the level of expansion and

the amount of expansion are determined by the appearance of the product or the pattern, first approximately, and then, during the trying on of the product on the figure, finally. Conical expansion is often used in conjunction with parallel expansion.

When modeling folds in complex draperies, it is recommended to use the dummy method.

Discussion of the results obtained and conclusions.

With an increase in the volume of the product, the nature of its supporting surface changes. An increase in the gaps between the figure and clothing on the chest line, as well as the introduction of shoulder pads,

leads to a greater, compared to the base, detachment of the lateral sections of the back and front from the surface of the figure, that is, on the back in the area of the shoulder blades and in front at the level of the chest line it decreases curvature of the surface. Structurally, such a model shape is achieved by reducing the solutions of the upper dart of the front and shoulder dart of the back, up to their complete elimination by modeling the basic darts. Under the modeling of a dart, transfer of any part of it into sections (armholes, necklines, bottom, etc.) in order to lengthen them, which allows you to get a flatter shape that does not emphasize the shape of the body.

Armhole modeling

The armhole is a functional important unit of a shoulder piece with a set-in sleeve.

Complex transformations of the design of one type of clothing into a design of another type are performed using typical designs of the closest type. Examples of

Its parameters and configuration determine: the projected shape of the back and front parts, the share of the total increase along the chest line coming to the section of the armhole, the design of the shoulder sections, the model sleeve width at the top, technological requirements, etc. Various combinations of these factors determine many options for model armholes.

Changing the cut of the sleeve involves combining the details of the set-in sleeve of the basic design with the details of the back and front for their subsequent dissection with new model lines. The most common examples of modeling a basic set-in sleeve design are conversions to raglan, one-piece, shirting, and combo designs using basic set-in sleeve designs.

obtaining new types of clothing on the basis of standard ones are capes, capes, overalls, skirts, trousers, shorts, swimming trunks and others.

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